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Deliverable D7.7
Second report on CoE infrastructure and service

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D7.7 Second report on CoE infrastructure and service

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Executive Summary

In this deliverable we report on the development of the CoE infrastructure and services, and illustrate the actions that were performed in months 7-24.

Concerning the infrastructure, we describe both the internal CoE operation and the functions oriented to end-users and the community at large. We also update the report on communication activities, and include an updated communication plan after two years of experience. Some criticalities in the management are discussed, together with some corrective actions.

Concerning services, we report on the advances in the delivery processes and examine the service acceptance among users. We also discuss the development of new services, most importantly the so-called “Quantum-as-a-service” (QaaS), and suggest some corrective and steering actions.

Finally, we discuss the results of the quality assessment of the infrastructure, and update the SWOT and the risk tables.

1. Activity report on CoE infrastructure

1.1. Management team and basic activities

In its first two years the Centre has been managed according to the principles and objectives described in the Grant Agreement and in Task 7.2.

The CoE **management team** has worked under the coordination of the executive manager, Dr. Guido Chiarotti, in tight connection with the MaX Director Elisa Molinari. The day-by-day work of the team has been structured operatively by thematic subgroups, dedicated to key aspects of the management. Among them, communication and dissemination (website, publicity, newsletter), services, IPR management, technical coordination of MaX developments (software, AiiDA integrated solutions, turn-key solutions), training and education (coordination of activities, calendars), EU reporting & project management. During the period, a few changes in the hired personnel within the technical secretariat have occurred. Dr. Nadja Sändig left the team and was replaced by Dr. Tommaso Portaluri for a few months. Dr. Portaluri left the team at the end of M23, and the new person hired, Dr. Maria Bartolacelli, will start at M25 (mid-September 2017). Despite the fact that these changes occurred in a small management team and in a short-term project such as MaX, no major consequences were detected. In the meantime, the work was taken over by other members of the management team: especially Dr. Luisa Neri, who is particularly experienced and strongly dedicated to this project, with major contributions also from other staff members (especially for the newsletter and the coordination of the training activities).

The main management action lines are reported in the following paragraphs, specifically devoted to supporting communication, training, dissemination activities, intellectual property management, and participation in EU and other concertation activities. In addition, management has taken care of:

- coordination of deliverable production and related reporting
- reporting for the “check meeting” held in Bruxelles on May 2016, including the production of a “MaX Spring 2016 booklet”
- reporting for the midterm review meeting (Apr 2017)
- organization, invitations and minutes of General Assembly meetings
- MaX presentation at several public meetings and dissemination events
- direct involvement in industrial outreach
- interaction with --and MaX presentations to-- institutional stakeholders (such as regional governments)

Importantly, the CoE management is closely following the general efforts of MaX to address the concerns raised by reviewers at midterm.

Concerning **interactions between WPs, especially WP5-WP7**, we have worked at a closer connection especially on aspects related to communication and dissemination, through systematic meetings and teleconferences of WP5 leader with management. Most of the results will be apparent in the next months but some are already visible in the updated communication plan and in the sections below.

Concerning the involvement of **other community codes as possible beneficiaries of MaX software** developments, one of MaX key goals as also remarked by the reviewers at midterm, the CoE management has acted by networking on one side and internally steering the software developments on the other. First, a number of domain specific libraries and community specific tools are going to be released soon (M24 and M30). Second, the teams involved in each of the codes are making specific

contacts and actions within the electronic structure and materials science community. In addition, the management has directly started interactions with two code developing teams, that we consider among the most prominent in view of the evolution towards the exascale: BigDFT (www.bigdft.org) and cp2k (www.cp2k.org). Both have significant technological overlap with MaX codes, mostly with Siesta and Quantum ESPRESSO respectively. In the case of BigDFT collaboration is already ongoing. We have agreed to further detail specific collaborations in the next future with these (and other) code teams.

Management is also addressing the issue of stronger promotion of **women within the CoE and beyond**, as mentioned informally during the review. At this stage of the project we can have only limited impact on MaX hiring, but all units are increasing their efforts concerning PhD students: we hope to see results of this process. At the same time, we are actively promoting the presence of women as prominent speakers in meetings, most notably in the main dissemination Conference that MaX is organizing in Trieste at the end of November 2017. Admission processes in our training events now take in greater account the diversity criterion (results hopefully to be seen in forthcoming events). A specific effort is ongoing with the ‘MaX Prize’ initiative (see also next section), established to attract input from MaX code users and to increase the visibility of achievements based on our flagship codes: the call explicitly invites women to participate and promises special attention to women applicants. We hope to see results in high quality women presence in the pool of applicants and in the final results of the selection process, expected at the end of October.

We are meanwhile continuing with policy initiatives, both at international and national levels. One emerging focus theme is that women in fields crossing different disciplines face common problems and barriers, so common actions could help to sensitize research institutions. In new fields at the boundary between women-rich and women-poor fields, it was observed

--e.g. in nano-bio-technology-- that the tendency is to conform to the worst (women-poor) side of the boundary. This calls for dedicated actions to limit and possibly overcome this trend. We previously contributed to this debate by emphasizing the specific case of frontier computational materials research (with the critical boundaries between physics/chemistry/materials-science and information technologies) within Global Research Council meetings (GRC, <http://www.globalresearchcouncil.org>), and are now continuing within some national initiatives. A dedicated talk by Molinari is e.g. foreseen at the national meeting of the Italian Physical Society on Sep 14, 2017.

Paris Meeting Computational Materials: Challenges and Future Opportunities, May 31st - June 2nd, 2017

1.2. Communication activities

Several internal and external communication activities have been performed by the CoE, especially by the leader group CNR, which hosts the management team and the people in charge of communication. The activity of the communication team during the period M7-M24 (Mar 2016-Aug 2017) has been twofold. On the one side, we have tried to convey to the public the idea of MaX as a user-focused, problem-oriented Centre of Excellence supporting the needs and vision of a number of players on HPC-oriented materials simulations. This has been a challenging task, as MaX keywords are not of easy grasping for the general public. About this, we have been working on crucial ideas for general audience communication such as the concept of materials combined with innovation and computer-design. On the other side, MaX is a lively network of well-established institutions and scientists, with many MaX-related ongoing activities and news that we have tried to spread to public.

A great effort has been made in working with the partners in order to develop a commitment to communication activities and boost the “multiplier effect” that is very useful in social and web communication. During M22-M23 (Jun-Jul 2017) we have coordinated two teleconference meetings with partners in order to define actions to be undertaken for the next few months, in order to be prepared to communicate about MaX results and achievements at best. Success stories, grand challenges, etc need to be prepared in advance in order to communicate. These meetings were highly participated and are definitely turning points in our communication activities, that will involve all our communication channels and partners.

1. Web presence

Web presence is crucial to MAX, for its network structure and for the amount and the diversity of information that we need to promote. MAX has four different and coordinated websites that permit to communication general-interest information or industry/user oriented information. One of the main tasks of the management team has been the continuous updating with institutional information about the CoE and MaX’s related news.

1. The principal website is the **MAX portal** (<http://www.max-centre.eu>) that provides the institutional information about the centre, its objectives, aims, services, trainings, people, as well as about news and events related to the CoE life. Some of them are events directly organized by MAX , others are considered of interest for the MAX public. It is continuously updated with news, events, info about MaX-related activities, and will soon undergo a renovation in order to enhance the visibility and use of codes.

In the last few months, M19-M24 (Mar-Aug 2017), the website has registered about 100.440 visits and 36.787 visitors, with about 11.000 references from browsers or other websites.

2. The MAX User portal (<http://userportal.max-centre.eu>) (MUP) is the operative part of the MaX Single User Entry Point (SUEP) strategy. It is accessible with clearly displayed links both from the MaX Industrial Website and the MaX Portal by authenticated users. MUP delivers the services provided by the CoE through a User Dashboard, and it has a rich back-office structure allowing for the SUEP administrator to manage the User Dashboard personalization (habilitated services, specific messages, etc.), and service organization and delivery. It was launched in February 2017, its home page is being restyled in order to make contents accessible to all users, even if it is necessary to

register to access all services for a better customization of the offer. To date, it counts more than 200 registered users.

MaX HELP-DESK
Direct contact help-desk service is intended for assistance on:

- Input preparation and output interpretation
- Code utilization (focus on performances and HPC optimization)
- Code personalization (small modifications)

To activate the Help-Desk Service please fill up this form

MaX ADVANCED SUPPORT
Direct contact help-desk service dedicated to HPC users (specifically for submission proposals):

- Specific technical issues (scaling, CPU and memory requirements)
- Guided choice of appropriate codes for specific research context

To activate the Advanced Support Service please fill up this form

Example of the service window as it appears in the User Portal (more about services in the next Section).

3. **Industrial website** (<https://max-centre.industries>). It is strictly connected with the official MaX project website, and provides content and presentation that are addressed to industrial potential users and are focussed on the European impact of MaX activities.
4. **Intranet** (<http://intranet.max-centre.eu>): the access-restricted Intranet Portal provides information, data, documents, KPI description, and communication facilities, reserved to the MaX internal community (around 70 users). It is based on the Google apps cloud technology with specific personalization. This is part of the setup of the CoE as an infrastructure. The service has been set up maintained by Cnr.

The entries in the Intranet repository.

The present structure with independent industrial portal was designed to allow for special focus on industrial users, with dedicated messages and language. After use, we are now planning readjustments that are discussed in the Appendix 1 “Updated communication plan”.

2. Social-media presence

Due to their intrinsically interactive nature, social-media represents a crucial communication instrument for MaX community building, which effectively reinforce and tune the MaX image and identity. Although the target scientific community is not yet very keen on this media channels, we opened a Twitter profile (@max_center2) and a LinkedIn company page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/max-center>) in order to address different publics and to convey contents that might not find a proper space in traditional websites.

Twitter account (@max_center2) is active from March 2016 (M7). It is the medium we use to produce or push topics that are relevant to our world in a lively and fast way, even though it is not very popular among scientists from the electronic structure and materials science community.

Since its opening, we have written 223 tweets, and have had 90.761 tweet visualizations and 6.708 visits to the profile. We reckon the number of followers is quite low, 144 to date, but most of them are institutions, companies, other projects, so have themselves an audience, and we are fastly improving interactions and followers by focussing on specific keywords of interest. Most of our tweets are about MaX activities, EU policies, HPC and supercomputing, codes, Women in Science, STEM, or HPC partners’ activities. For example, the whole MaX meeting

held in Trieste last January was covered by live tweets with pictures and a dedicated hashtag #MaXmeeting.

We made a great effort to have all partners involved in the Twitter activities, by asking them to provide contents or retweet our tweets (multiplier effects). MaX in Twitter is always cited as #MaX_CoE. The embedded timeline is also available in the website home page.

The **LinkedIn** company page has been thought as a complementary tool for connecting with companies and possible stakeholders. As a tool it is less flexible than Twitter, but gives us the chance of entering a different environment. As an example, the white paper “Designing Materials with High Performance Computing”, that got 21 shares, has been quite effective. Job posts have also been pushed via LinkedIn. To date, we have published 34 posts and have 61 followers. The post with the highest number of interactions, very successful in Twitter and in the website as well, has been the one about the *MaX prize* (see below).

3. Newsletter

In February 2017 we launched our first newsletter, whose core target has been the scientific and computing community, and, at large, stakeholders and institutions.

So far three numbers of the newsletter have been published, all structured around success cases, with emphasis on industry collaborations. In addition, the newsletter includes information about MaX services and training activities. According to the communication shift that will be further discussed in the communication plan (see Appendix 1), the newsletter is focussed on codes, exascale, and co-design.

The newsletter is drafted and distributed via mailchimp to a dedicated mailing list. It is

also circulated through some community mailing lists (such as PsiK and ETSF) and through the communication channels of the codes (the mailing list of Quantum ESPRESSO alone reaches about 3000

people worldwide; Similarly for the Siesta user basin). Currently it has more than 570 subscribers, a constantly growing number as shown in the chart above.

MaX CoE @max_center2 · 8 ago
 The new feature for #Siesta or the new #Fleur benchmark on the RWTH compute CLAIX cluster in #MaX_CoE #2 newsletter max-centre.eu/newsletter/
 Traduci dalla lingua originale: inglese

Focus on MaX flagship codes
A new feature for Siesta: including spin-orbit interaction

The MaX ICN2 team has recently implemented the calculation of the spin-orbit interaction in SIESTA. New protocols were tested to describe the interaction between magnetic and electric properties of materials. The new implemented capabilities, together with the flexibility of SIESTA, open new possibilities in the study of systems where the spin-orbit interaction is crucial, and in the computational design of new magneto-electric materials. Interesting results were already obtained e.g. in the case of energy-efficient magnetic actuation. The last version of SIESTA, including such developments, is available to download from the [MaX user portal](#). [See more...](#)

An example of integrated promotion of the newsletter (08/08/2017 Tweet)

The newsletter is also promoted via our social media and in the website, where it can be consulted at the address <http://www.max-centre.eu/newsletter/>.

4. MaX Prize for frontier HPC application in materials research

The first MaX prize “for frontier HPC application in materials research” was issued in July 2017 and will be open until the end of September 2017. The prize answers to a double need: on the one hand, the necessity to put in the spotlight several excellent and innovative activities that are done with our flagship codes, both in academia and industry; on the other hand, the need to convey the message that our codes - and the related research - have an impact out of the labs.

This prize is open to scientists performing frontier research, enabled by MaX flagship codes worldwide, with a special emphasis on industrial researchers, women scientists, students and young researchers. The prize recipient(s) will have the chance to present their research to the upcoming MaX conference in Trieste (November 2017).

MaX prize for frontier HPC applications in materials research - 2017

The prize has been ideated, following an original suggestion by Prof. S. Baroni (SISSA), organized and promoted by the MaX management and communication teams. It has been promoted in the August issue of the MaX newsletter, in the website through a dedicated webpage (<http://www.max-centre.eu/2017/07/18/prize/>), with a pinned Tweet, and with a post in LinkedIn. The news has also been shared in the Partner institutional websites, sent to the code mailing lists and by way of personalized tweets. MaX speakers at conferences and in schools have advertised the price by showing a dedicated slide.

To date, the page in the MaX website is the second most visited (963 visits), the Tweet about the Prize is the most popular (4995 views and 12 retweets), and has had several interactions in the newsletter and LinkedIn as well. The campaign about the prize will be intensified towards the deadline in September, but interactions are a clear proof of a successful communication effort.

5. Non-media communication activities

Non-media communications as the organisation and participation to congresses and schools, the participation at trade fairs, meetings with companies, and possibly the organisation of cultural events (exhibitions, etc.) are particularly effective for promoting both MaX services and the MaX image (see

D7.5). When coupled with social-media communications, these non-media-events will act as effective amplifiers of social media coverage.

From December 2016 to March 2017, for example, CNR and University of Modena and Reggio Emilia participated to the event “Into the Future”, an initiative addressing high-school students who visited their premises for one morning and were introduced to nanosciences and some possible career paths in research. About 120 students attended the lectures in which frontier computational developments in materials science including the role of MaX were presented, and one of the MaX pilot actions was the subject of a hands-on working group which attracted great interest from the students. The program was integrated with social media pages, see eg

https://twitter.com/max_center2/status/829649878494113792

1.3. Support to dissemination activities

MaX dissemination activity is quite rich and performed by all partners in different ways. It is addressed at researchers and academia (for the latter see D7.5), as well as to industrial end-users (see D5.3). MaX members have given invited and contributed talks to conferences, workshops, and seminars, covering all range of subjects related to the CoE activity (from methodological developments to improvement of HPC performances and technology exploitation, to cutting edge computational studies of scientific test cases). Some talks have especially focussed on the CoE structure particularly within the ecosystem of e-infrastructures. Selected examples are:

- Designing Materials with High Performance Computing.
Guido Chiarotti (CNR Nano). International Conference of Synthetic Population. Lucca (IT). 02/02/2017
- Materials design at the exascale. The MaX Centre of Excellence.
Elisa Molinari (CNR Nano). Big Data Table of Regione Emilia Romagna, Bologna (IT). 03/02/2017
- Designing materials with High Performance Computing.
Carlo Cavazzoni (Cineca). EoCoE project meeting. Rome (IT). 02/12/2016
- Materials design at the exascale.
Andrea Ferretti (CNR). Brazil MRS 2016. Campinas, Sao Paulo (BR). 28/09/2016
- MaX Centre of Excellence: Materials at the Exascale.
Pablo Ordejón (ICN2). E-CAM Industry Meeting. Mainz (DE). 07/09/2016

Other main dissemination activities (co)organized are:

- XVIII Total ENergy and Force Methods Conference, Trieste, IT - January 2017
- MaX general meeting, Trieste (IT), Jan. 10-11, 2017. It is widely described in Par. 3 of D7.5. The meeting was organized by Cnr with a strong support by SISSA.
- CNR and ICTP are currently organizing the MaX Conference that will take place in trieste next November 2017.
- “Juelich, MARVEL, MaX get together on AiiDA and its application for Material Design”, organized by EPFL & Juelich, Juelich, DE, November 2016.

- “Material Science codes on innovative HPC architectures: targeting exascale @Cineca”, organized by Cineca in Bologna, IT, December 2016.

An important effort has been made by the management team about the spread and fulfilment of the H2020 Open Access policy among partners. All scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals referred to MaX are now compliant with the H2020 open access rules. A vademecum about open access rules has been prepared and circulated among partners, and is always available to them in the Intranet. A person in the staff operates as contact point for partners for OA questions.

1.4. Support to training activities

Within the tasks of WP6, MaX partners have organized so far 11 training schools and hands-on tutorials, attended by more than 450 researchers from academia and industry. The management and the local nodes have strongly supported the practical organization of schools, and the related communication activities. See <http://www.max-centre.eu/training-and-education> for more details.

1.5. Intellectual Property management

The Management team has also coordinated the handling of IPR issues, with special care when industrial companies were involved. Early during the infrastructure setup, a protocol for the engagement with external customers for the delivery of services has been defined and approved by the GA. Among other points discussed, the management of IPR when dealing with commercial partners applying or paying for MaX services has been agreed and structured. In doing this and in the specific cases deal with afterwards, the experience done working with the companies involved in the Pilot projects of MaX WP2 has been particularly relevant.

At a different level, IPR management was also needed in connection with software development. In one case, the SIESTA code, that was not open source before MaX, made the transition to GPL Licence, completing the process by about M9 (May 2016). This has required a dedicated work to reach consensus and a formal agreement among the code developers. In the case of Quantum ESPRESSO, already GPL before MaX, IPR handling was needed because of a contract signed with Schrodinger, a private company providing integrated software solutions to scientists and modellers. In this case the MaX management has taken advantage of the experience in open source IPR handling of Carlo Daffara, PI of CloudWeavers, a MaX partner.

Non-disclosure agreements (NDA's) have been signed with SIMUNE and the Quantum ESPRESSO Foundation in order to further push the possibility of leveraging open source software as Siesta and Quantum ESPRESSO on the market. At the same time, NDA's have also been submitted for signature to the members of the IAB (International advisory board), which are in part from companies, and are supposed to provide feedback and recommendation about MaX activities. See Deliverable D7.6 for further details.

1.6. Participation in EU and other concertation/policy activities

MaX has been extremely active in participating in EU and other concertation activities since its establishment. It has interacted with other CoEs, European and local governing bodies. The main activities are listed below:

- participation to 1st EMMC European Materials Modelling Council International Workshop 2017, Vienna, Austria, 5-7 April 2017.

<https://emmc.info/the-first-emmc-international-workshop-2017/>

- Paris Meeting - Computational Materials: Challenges and Future Opportunities, May 31st - June 2nd, 2017. <http://paris-meeting-2017.uchicago.edu/>

The directors and senior principal investigators of computational materials science centers worldwide met from May 31st to June 2nd in Paris, together with representatives of major computational materials projects. The meeting, hosted by Giulia Galli at the University of Chicago Paris Center, discussed main challenges and future directions, as well as strategies and possible collaborations in the field of computational materials research, and agreed to work on a joint statement. MaX was present with E. Molinari, P. Ordejon, N. Marzari and T. Schulthess.

- European Open Science Cloud Summit. Brussels, Belgium. 12 June 2017. E. Molinari (see picture).

<http://ec.europa.eu/research/index.cfm?eventcode=44D86060-FBA1-1BD1-9355822B162BB0EE&pg=events>

- “Europe as a global player in High Performance Computing”, Digital Day, the digital part of the official celebrations marking the 60th anniversary of the Treaties of Rome, Rome (IT), 23 March 2017. E. Molinari.

<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/europe-global-player-high-performance-computing-digital-day>

- >10 meetings of Regione Emilia Romagna (IT) “Big data” concertation table; coordination of the working group Materials chapter in booklet “From volume to value” of the Emilia Romagna Big Data Community. 2017. E. Molinari. <http://www.aster.it/pubblicazioni/volume-value>
- ETP4HPC: participation in meetings, and contributions to the Strategic Research Agenda on many key aspects.

We also mention one specific action promoted by MaX, with focus and possible impact on policies. A workshop entitled *Synergy between quantum computing and high-performance computing* was organized in Zurich on August 22-24, 2017, in collaboration with CECAM. Further information is visible at <https://www.cecam.org/workshop-0-1464.html>, and the full program at <https://www.cecam.org/workshop-2-1464.html>. The workshop included top-level speakers from academia and industry, with a very strong industrial component. It was also designed as an opportunity for brainstorming, and indeed we had excellent discussion sessions on perspectives of quantum computing and its interfaces with HPC from the point of view of materials and quantum chemistry simulations, and related policy issues. A report on these points is in preparation.

2. Activity report on services (update)

The Users Portal has been set up and launched in February 2017.

MaX services are delivered through the User Portal, which is continuously evolving adding more services and improving user interactions. At the moment of writing the 6 basic services (CODE DOWNLOADING, BASIC SUPPORT, HELP-DESK, ADVANCED SUPPORT, ADVANCED CONSULTING, DEDICATED TRAINING) have been integrated by a Jupyter scientific notebook which is directly accessible from inside the User Portal. This is intended to be the support for the QaaS (Quantum-as-a-Service) delivery process. The service is currently under testing (see D7.8 “Business plan assessment and revision” for technical details particularly on the multi-user active notebook interface).

Moreover, to promote the User Portal access among users, it was decided that the two low-level services of codes and workflows downloading and forum-based basic support will also be accessible from outside the portal through a dedicated space in the institutional website.

2.1. Processes

The two main manned processes related to the User Portal delivered services were completely defined and tested among users. For organizational reasons both processes are still in a provisional stage (delivered only by CINECA at level 2). The MaX internal document outlining these processes is reported below:

Beginning of the document:

This document describes a MaX process.

MAX HELP-DESK

MAX HELP-DESK is a three-level support service with single (unmanned) MAX user entry point.

The support is intended to shorten the time to develop and to deliver scientific cases implying code utilisation, and to increase user base of the supported MaX-codes (YAMBO, SIESTA, QUANTUM ESPRESSO, FLEUR, and AiiDA + other codes in the material science domain to be defined in the future), facilitating codes utilisation and optimal resources utilization. MaX will assist the potential code user in:

- (i) Code utilisation, with particular attention on optimal - HPC focussed - use and performances.
- (ii) Input preparation and output interpretation.
- (iii) Implementation of small code modification upon request (code personalisation).

All procedures will be restricted to specific class of subscribers (to be defined), some eventually upon payments. The procedure can be activated by an online form on the MaX website or by standard email to helpdesk@max-center.eu. The online form will contain various menus, in order to facilitate the insertion of the requests. The answers will be arranged in an order aimed at the construction of a knowledge-base directly accessible by the code community. The possibility to implement different activation paths, eventually directly from the TTS of the computer center partners, upon requests non passing through the MAX single entry point will also be considered.

PROCESS:

Help-desk like procedure:

Unmanned single entry point (**level 1**) reserved to specific class of users will automatically forward the user request to the to the level 2.

Level 2 (operated by computer centres affiliated to MaX, with frequency rotation - weekly or multiple - to be determined on the basis of the dedicated effort as defined in the Grant Agreement). This level solves the issues relative to actions (i) (ii) and (iii) scaling up when necessary. This level will be responsible for the openings and the closures of all the issues. In final deployment regime MaX computer centres will implement this level on a weekly basis turn.

Level 3 (operated by MaX scientists): The assigned scientist (or group of scientists) will resolve the instances due to scaling up. Level 3 can be activated by level 1 only.

The provisional deployment regime level 2 will be operated only by CINECA (no rotation). In this regime the personnel of the other MAX computer centres can be activated at level 2.

MAX ADVANCED SUPPORT

MAX ADVANCED SUPPORT is a two-level support service with manned single user entry point. The service is intended for increasing the use of HPC in computer materials simulations favouring improving code performances, optimal resources and appropriate code utilisation.

The service is reserved to applications involving the MaX supported codes (YAMBO, SIESTA, QUANTUM ESPRESSO, and FLEUR).

In particular, the MaX experts will assist the applicants:

- 1) To develop technical/scientific aspects (code-related) of national, European and international proposals
- 2) To choose the appropriate software in respect to the research context.
- 3) To analyse the scalability properties of the codes;
- 4) To establish the adequacy of requested CPU time.

All procedures will be restricted to specific class of subscribers, some eventually upon payments. The procedure will be activated by standard email to support@max-center.eu

PROCESS: Manned MaX single user-entry point (**level 1**) forward to level 2 the request with the indication of the resolution procedure: (three indications possible: (p.1) to be solved at level 2; or (p.2) forward to specific level 3 researcher or distribution list; or (p.3) no indications).

Level 2 (operated by computer centres affiliated to MaX, with frequency rotation - weekly or multiple - to be determined on the basis of the dedicated effort as defined in the Grant Agreement). This level operates according to the indications of the single entry point. In case of state p.3 (no indications) try to solve issues scaling up when necessary. This level will be responsible for the activation and the closure

of all the issues. In final deployment regime all MaX computer centres will implement this level on a weekly basis turn.

Level 3 (operated by MaX scientists): The assigned scientist will try to resolve the issues Level 3 can be activated only by level 2.

The provisional deployment regime level 1 will be operated only by CINECA (no rotation). In this regime the personnel of the other MAX computer centres can be activated at level 3.

END of the document

2.2 Perspectives and corrective actions

As common in developing new service modes, acceptance within the community is a challenging goal. This is a well known problem, largely debated in innovation literature, and it is related to the difficulty of shifting the users/customers base from the old operative mode to the new one. This issue is less critical when introducing a completely new (disrupting) service, which occupies a well defined (empty) user niche. It is much more critical for services which build on pre-existing processes, with only a slight improvement on user/customer perception. This is unfortunately the case for some of the services provided so far through the MaX User Portal, which are evolutions of services separately offered by the individual codes.

We expect this situation to radically change as soon as we will start providing the QaaS service through the User Portal. **QaaS is in fact expected to be a more disruptive service with respect to those implemented up to now.**

Meanwhile, we are improving the User Portal to make more information available before login, and we are working on communication actions that will be integrated more tightly in the general communication of the Centre (see Communication plan update, in Appendix 1). A good example in that direction is represented by the news on the portal that are reported in every issue of the MaX newsletter.

3. KPIs at M18

The last KPIs collection was made at M18. The next KPI collection will be performed during M25, and will refer to values at M24. Since the procedure to collect and calculate the KPIs is quite demanding, we decided not to perform an ad-hoc collection for this deliverable, and to present here the M18 collection comparing its values both with the targets at M18 and M24. You can notice that many of the KPIs at M18 are already above the targets at M24. More comments can be found in the next paragraph.

KPI #	Key performance indicator	KPI definition	Type of data required	Start at Month	Value at M12	Target at M18	Value at M18	Target at M24
1	INFRASTRUCTURE: Codes Maintenance & Availability	Measure of the maintenance activity and availability of the MaX WP1-codes (Quantum Engines plus PALENQUE socket interface)	Number of public releases of the MaX WP1-Codes (Quantum Engines plus PALENQUE socket interface)	M1	12	15	20	20
2	SERVICES: Number of End-Users (advanced services)	Number of End-Users taking advantage of the MaX advanced services, including software, support, consulting, education and training	Number of End-Users for MaX-operated advanced services. NOTE: the users of download and basic support services are not included here: see KPI # 5.	M6	180	200	470	350
3	SERVICES DEVELOPMENT: Catalogue of Services	Measure the number of Operated Services	Number of services offered through MaX Users Portal	M6	6	6	6	8
4	SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT: New implemented features and Cross Code Integration	Measure the new features implemented in the Flagship Codes including those devoted to Cross Code Integration	Number of new features implemented in the Flagship Codes as reported in the development agenda, including self standing modules (counted one for each code)	M6	12	12	18	16
5	ECOSYSTEM: Number of end users	Measure of impact of the Flagship Codes	Maximum value among: Number of unique downloads of the flagship	M8	10680	11000	9454 (*)	11500

	for basic services and Impact of MaX Codes		codes per year; Number of journal citations of MaX reference code papers per year; Number of forum/ mailing list subscribers					
6	EXASCALE: Co-design	Number of performance measurements (a single performance measurement is intended as a table of data relative to a single app on a single architecture, collected with different run configurations of threads and tasks)	Performance curves (energy to solution, time to solution, system exploitation)	M8	5	10	8	15
7	EXASCALE: Exploitation	Maximum HPC system partition exploited (in Pflop/s)	Size of the maximum partition exploited per each code. Reference data will be taken from the performance curves of KPI-6	M8	1.0	1.0	1.5	1.25
8	DATA: Data Management	Measure of the size of the collected data in the open MaX repository of materials data, workflows, turn-key solutions, and protocols (as defined by D3.5)	Number of Nodes in the AiiDA database graph technically underlying the open MaX repository	M18	-	10 ⁴	NA	10 ⁵
9	DISSEMINATION: Schools, Conferences, Publications	Participation upon invitation of MaX scientists to Schools, Workshops and Conferences plus Publications	Total number of invited talks to Conferences and Schools + Total number of publications acknowledging MaX (or given/authored by MaX scientists). Organisations of conferences are counted as invited.	M8	85	80	112	120
10	DISSEMINATION / OUTREACH: Contacts and Visits to industrial entities and Presentations to Industrial Events	Measure the MaX activity on industries	MCII (MaX Contact Industry Index) = 1* (Total number of firms contacted by MaX via replied emails or telephone calls) + 10* (Total number of MaX visit to single industrial entities) + 100* (Total number of	M8	142	500	988	750

			Presentations to industrial events and sectorial fairs)					
11	DISSEMINATION / TRAINING: Training Courses	Participants' Feedback on Training Courses organised by MaX	Average Evaluation assigned by Participants in questionnaires [value between 1 (negative) and 5 (optimum)]	M13	4.5*	>3.5	4.3	>3.5
12	DISSEMINATION / EXPLOITATION: Community Building	Activities on Social and Technical Communities measured in terms of Followers, Sharings, Likes, Traffics, Click-Throughs, Comments, Subscribers, Posts	1* Total Number of followers (twitter, linkedIn) + 10* received comments (twitter, linkedIn, newsletter and/or blog) + 10 * subscribers (newsletter, LinkedIn groups, new forums) + 1* technical forum posts (flagship codes related forums)	M13	-	100	102(^)	300
13	EXPLOITATION: Business Performance	Industry projects promoted by MaX	Total number of contracts and/or official agreements with industrial partners promoted by MaX	M6	2	6	3	10
14	PROCESS: Knowledge Base Documentation/Best Practices	Number of documents defining the MaX knowledge Base and documenting MaX Best Practices	Total number of documents managing the MaX knowledge Base and documenting MaX Best Practices	M6	2	4	3	6

(*)The user's counting procedure has been revised to better count users in presence of more software releases in the analyzed period. The old counting procedure, on the basis of which the M18 target was established, gives 23.150, well above the M18 target (11.000).

(^) The user's counting procedure has been revised to adjust to the actual response to communication activities. In particular the calculation of “comments”, i.e., a response to a post, not common for the kind of informative posts we usually write, has been replaced by the assessment of engagement by way of “interactions” with posts (that is, clicks on, likes, comments, shares). Secondly, the “technical forum” posts (though very numerous, see WP5 description) are not counted, as we consider important for impact our interaction via social media with a broad community (from the citizen to the expert). The given number represents an average number and refers to M18. The old counting procedure, on the basis of which the M18 target was established, has been reconsidered as the results was well above the M18 target (result = 10.282, target = 100) by normalizing the result by 100. Therefore, we have changed the definition of “Type of data required” as follows “1* Total Number of followers (twitter, linkedIn+user portal+MaX newsletter-internal) + 10* received comments interactions (Twitter, LinkedIn, newsletter and/or blog: sum of clicks on link, shares, likes, comments) + 10 * subscribers (newsletter, LinkedIn groups, user portal, new forums) + 1* technical forum posts (flagship codes related forums Twitter, LinkedIn).

3.1 KPIs at M18: some considerations and comments

As noticed above, most of the values of MaX KPIs at M18 were already very close or even above their target values at M24, meaning that the Centre is performing well. Exceptions to this observation are represented by KPIs 3, 5, 6, 7, 12, 13 and 14. In the following these are discussed in details.

KPI-3 (services development): the value of this KPI at M18 is in line with target at M18, but below the target at M24. This lower value will be confirmed also by the collection at M24, and is due to a change in the strategy of service implementation: instead of increasing the number of the deployed services, MaX has chosen to put more effort in developing a brand new service, not available in other platforms. As previously stated, this is mainly due to the difficulty of making the users shift from their traditional service operational modes to the new proposed ones - the User Portal's - containing little innovation. At

this stage, the main innovation is related to manned help desk, but such an advantage has not yet been perceived by our expert customer base. Thus, we concentrated on developing the QaaS delivery mode, that is expected to be a more disruptive innovation in terms of fruition of MaX capabilities. From now on, this will be the only service added to the User Portal and this KPI will probably remain underperforming.

KPI-5 (ecosystem): this value is below the expectations due to a change in the measurement. This new measure is more realistic, but targets will be affected. The M24 value will be the benchmark to decide whether to change the target values.

KPI-6 (co-design): this value was only slightly below its target at M18: we expect that it will remain slightly below the M24 target also with the collection at M24. An effort will be put in place specifically on this issue to put that in line with the target at M30.

KPI-12 (community-building): the value at M18 complies with M18 target, and is below the M24 target. Due to the increased effort on social media in the last months, we expect the value at M24 value to be in line with its target.

KPI-13 (business performance): this is the most critical discrepancy: the number of signed contracts at M18 is below the expectations at M18 and at M24 will also be significantly smaller than the target a. The value of this KPI can be contrasted with that KPI-10 which takes into account the number of contacts with companies, which is well above its target values. There is a bottleneck in transforming *contacts* in *contracts*, possibly due to an immaturity of the MaX technology in terms of market value, and/or to an inefficient “commercial” process. The true innovative service we are planning (QaaS) should soon enter the market and mend this situation. Being the market acceptance of QaaS hypothetical and being the release of the product close to the project end, it is not certain that it will be able to affect this underperformance in a significant way.

KPI-14 (Knowledge Base): the value at M18 is only slightly below its target at M18. Since a certain activity was put in place on this issue during the last months, we already know that the M24 value will be in line with its M24 target.

4. SWOT and Risks tables update

The Consortium considers **Risk management** an integral part of the project lifecycle, useful to minimize possible deviations from the expected results and schedule. Specific Risks and Contingency plans are defined for each WP are presented and discussed in the DoA (Par 1.3.5) and are further defined in D7.2 - par 3.2.

At the end of RP1, the quality of project outputs has been assessed by:

- a) evaluating the WPs’ objectives in terms of status of implementation and compliance with the Description of Action (DoA, see above);
- b) identifying quantitative indicators (KPIs) and assessing their numbers.

The procedure for the risk assessment, performed in October 2016 via the compilation of the Risk Assessment Tables (RAT), followed these steps:

- step 1:** identification of project risks additional to the ones forecasted at proposal stage
- step 2:** identification of one or more mitigation actions for each risk;

step 3: evaluation of each identified risk, using a scale from 1 to 5, according to the following parameters: criticality, importance, probability and impact.

step 4: updating both the MAX SWOT, determined for the first time at M6 (D7.2) and the RAT reported in the DoA.

For clarity, we report here the SWOT draft at M6 (see D7.2 section 3.5), followed by the SWOT redraft at M18, in which changes are properly highlighted. We also provide an explanation for such differences, describing how they have been determined (mainly as a result of the analysis of the KPIs at M18), and suggesting relevant mitigation or corrective actions. Similarly, we evaluated and analyzed the RAT, that has been expanded with new columns to indicate new evaluation of risk and probability, new mitigation actions.

Reading the KPIs, it is very easy to understand that the greatest part of risks listed in the DoA are unchanged, or are now lower than initially foreseen.

The risk that has grown more significantly is related to the timespan of the project (it is indicated in the Weakness section of the SWOT table as *Limited time span of MaX project (WP5, WP6)*). As it is evident from a comparison between KPI-10 (Outreach), well above the target at M18, with KPI-13 (signed contract), lower than its expected value. Such data clearly point out that the time needed in order to transform the very effective effort of MaX outreach (prospective customers) into signed contracts (consolidated customers) overcomes the actual timespan of the project. From an internal point of view, such bias between the values of KPI-10 and KPI-13 warns the CoE of a structural criticality of its, namely that lacking of a legal entity profile as a whole, it encounters difficulties in transforming the value proposition along the value chain, lacking the terminal part of it.

SWOT at M18 with variations with respect to M6

	HELPFUL	HARMFUL
INTERNAL	<p>Strengths due to MAX</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capability to manage shared data and workflows • Capability to develop and validate new technologies • Capability to manage IPR • Wide coverage of IT skills • Co-design Capabilities • Flexible Service Offer • Large users base of flagship codes • Capability in sw implement (WP1, WP3, WP5) • Codes easy for modularization (WP1, WP4) 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulties in s/w implementation (WP1, WP3, WP5) • Codes too entangled for modularization (WP1, WP4) • Limited time span of MaX project (WP5, WP6) (Higher at M18) • Underestimation of workload (all WPs) • Difficulty to attract new users to the User Portal (UP) (conservative users prefer their own tools)
EXTERNAL	<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New emerging technologies (WP1, WP3, WP4) • Excess of user's response (WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6) • Resolution of bugs emerging in HTC (WP3) and HPC (WP1, WP4) • New emerging co-design strategies (WP4) • New emerging HPC architectures (WP1, WP3, WP4) 	<p>Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unexpected emerging standards (WP1, WP3, WP4) • Lack on users response (WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6) (Higher at M18) • Reticence of industries (WP2, WP3, WP5) (Higher on M18, Surveying industrial users needs is difficult and time consuming and because attracting users to new services it complex) • Licence restriction due to platforms (WP4) • Availability of co-design H/W (WP4) • End users limited interest in training and industrial services (WP5, WP6)

Motivations for variations from M6 to M24 and suggested mitigation actions.

An analysis of the progression of the project in early 24 months, of actions undertaken and results obtained, led to the reorganization of the risk plan expressed in the SWOT table.

- **Strengths** were all confirmed as they are crucial to the project and assessed. Two points have been added and turned in from the Weakness list.
 - **Capability in s/w implementation** (WP1, WP3, WP5) was **Weakness: Difficulties in s/w implementation** (WP1, WP3, WP5). Being the result of KPI-1 “**INFRASTRUCTURE: Codes Maintenance & Availability** measured by the number of public releases of the MaX WP1-Codes (Quantum Engines plus PALENQUE socket interface)” higher than expected (20 at M18, expected 15), we reassessed the item and considered it a strength.
 - **Codes easy for modularization** (WP1, WP4) was **Weakness: Codes too entangled for modularization** (WP1, WP4). Being the result of KPI-4 “**SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT: New implemented features and Cross Code Integration**” well higher than expected (50% more: 18 instead of 12 at M18), we reassessed the item and considered the ability of modularization a point of strength of the network.
- **Weaknesses** were partly redefined as disproved by experience and by higher KPI numbers than expected.
 - **Codes too entangled for modularization** (WP1, WP4) and **Difficulties in s/w implementation** (WP1, WP3, WP5) have turned into **Strengths** as explained above.
 - **Underestimation of workload** (all WPs) has been cancelled as all KPIs have given proof of the fact the activities are having a great rate of success and are being managed properly.
 - **Limited time span of MaX project** (WP5, WP6) (Higher at M18). Though most of MaX activities are being performed sharp on time and impact is measurable through results and KPIs, it is more evident now at M18 that outreach and development of users’ awareness will take a longer time than MaX time span.

Mitigation actions: Having reached a perceivable maturity in our activities and services, in the last part of the project we will push more on dissemination, exploitation and outreach in order to reach as many industries as possible and take the greatest advantage from this time span. This criticality also emerges by confronting the values of KPI-10 (Outreach), well above the target at M18, with KPI-13 (signed contract), below its expected value: this clearly indicates that more time is needed to transform the very effective effort of MaX-outreach (prospective customers) into signed contracts (consolidated customers).
 - **Difficulty to attract new users to the User Portal (UP) (conservative users prefer their own tools)**. As explained transversally to this SWOT, a major difficulty we encountered, and according to KPI-2, KPI-3, KPI-4, KPI-5 we overcame, has been making industrial possible users aware of the advantage they can take from our services and codes. Moreover, many users turned out to be quite conservative and not very open to use tools different from theirs.

Mitigation actions: A more impactful strategy of communication will be adopted. Traditional communication materials, centered on the User portal, will be developed to make the services more visible. A major activity of outreach (e.g., presence at industrial fairs and meetings) will help this process.

The introduction of Quantum-as-a-Service will, on the one hand add a significative service to our set, on the other will serve as a gateway for boosting the knowledge and interest in the whole group of services.

- **Opportunities.** After 24 months of activity it has been possible to better understand what elements from the outside we could exploit to our advantage, and a reassessment of opportunities, on the basis of performed work and interactions with the environment, led us to some minor changes.
 - **Excess of user's response** (WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6): some WPs were removed from Opportunities because response was not excessively high, as inferred, e.g., by the partial difficulty encountered in the observatory activity (see deliverable D2.1). Nonetheless, we consider this a slight weakness for, once established and consolidated services and activities, we are going to put more effort in communicating them to target audiences (possible users). This will lead to a stronger impact and a wider and more poignant capability of intercepting user's needs.
 - **Threats.** A deeper knowledge of the environment led us also to a new evaluation of Threats. Symmetrically to what aforementioned, we had to change items connected to the expected response of public, in both positive and negative ways.
 - **Lack on users response** (WP2, ~~WP3~~, WP5, ~~WP6~~) (Higher at M24) and **End-users limited interest in training and industrial services** (WP5, WP6). As proved by KPI-2 "SERVICES: Number of End-Users (advanced services)" end-users taking advantage of the MaX advanced services, including software, support, consulting, education and training were more than double than expected (470 instead of 200 at M24). Nonetheless, several activities and events are already under preparation, as outreach, impact, and consolidation of the audience are of paramount importance for this CoE. **Mitigation actions:** A more impactful strategy of communication will be adopted. Traditional communication materials, centered on the User portal, will be developed to make the services more visible. A major activity of outreach (e.g., presence at industrial fairs and meetings) will help this process.
 - Reticence of industries** (WP2, WP3, WP5). We reckon this threat to be higher on M24, as surveying industrial users needs is difficult and time consuming and because attracting users to new services is complex.
 - Mitigation actions:** A more impactful strategy of communication will be adopted. Traditional communication materials, centered on the User portal, will be developed to make the services more visible. A major activity of outreach (e.g., presence at industrial fairs and meetings) will help this process.
- The introduction of Quantum-as-a-Service will, on the one hand add a significative service to our set, on the other will serve as a gateway for boosting the knowledge and interest in the whole group of services. Besides, penetration in the industry is a multifaceted problem, with many factors influencing the reticence of industries towards including simulation in their design and development flows. Our participation in networks and events with strong industrial component are helping us understand these difficulties, as a first step to design strategies for overcoming them, and to further enhance our interaction with and service to the industry.

Risk Assessment Table (RAT) update.

#	Description of Risk	Prob. M1	Imp. M1	WP	Proposed Risk mitigation actions	Prob. M24	Imp. M24	Motivations of variation and corrective actions for mitigation
R1	Among few demonstrated technologies to be adopted it is not clear which options are going to persist and become standards (<i>medium risk</i>)	MED	MED	WP1, WP3, WP4	WP1, WP3 will work in direct connection with WP4 concerning all technological issues; the modularisation of the codes and the adoption of domain-specific libraries will minimise the impact.	MED	MED	No indication of disruptive technology emerging.
R2	The existing structure of the codes is found to be too entangled to be fully modularised with a reasonable effort (<i>risk low</i>)	LOW	MED	WP1, WP4	Modularisation strategies will be carefully planned and designed before implementation actions	LOW-	MED	The value of KPI-4, well above the M18 target and near to final M30 target, indicates a diminished probability of occurring of this risk.
R3	Lack of response of the users' community to raise specific needs (<i>low risk</i>)	LOW	MED	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6, WP7	An appropriate outreach activity, in close coordination with WP5, promoting awareness of the potential solution of specific user needs and challenges upon request should minimise the risk of low response	MED	MED	The partial difficulty encountered in the observatory activity (see deliverable D2.1) justifies the risk increase. NEW MITIGATION ACTION: increase efforts in promoting awareness of potential solution. NEW MITIGATION ACTION: accelerate the QaaS development to create specific SMEs user's cases.
R4	Reticence of the industrial sector to share sensitive proprietary information	HIGH	MED	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP7	Specific Non-Disclosure Agreements will be signed whenever deemed necessary to	HIGH	MED	The risk is unchanged.

	necessary to specify their needs and to define appropriate validation cases (<i>high risk</i>)				safeguard the confidential information disclosed by the users. Typically protocols to solve specific problems will be made public while data will be kept confidential.			
R5	The realisation of an effective web repository for workflows/data may take longer than expected (<i>low risk</i>)	LOW	LOW	WP3, WP5, WP7	Interfaces to already-existing repositories, such as the COD/TCOD, can be developed to be able to contribute to open repositories without the need to develop a new web portal	LOW	LOW	The risk is unchanged.
R6	Intellectual property restrictions on the platforms used in T4.3 will not permit to release data publicly (<i>low risk</i>)	LOW	LOW	WP3, WP4, WP5, WP7	Agreement will be established in advance with vendors to decide which data can be publicly released	LOW	LOW	The risk is unchanged.
R7	Hardware platforms for T4.3 will be not available during the time span of the project (<i>low risk</i>)	LOW	LOW	WP1, WP4, WP7	Available hardware will be used and the work plan will be modified in order to permit other tests on new platforms whenever they will be ready.	LOW-	LOW	The hardware platform for T4.3 are available starting from M13.
R8	The access of users to the CoE services is delayed respect to the MAX timeline or limited (<i>low risk</i>)	LOW	HIGH	WP2, WP5, WP6, WP7	The actions aimed at getting in touch with possible users and customers (outreach events,	MED	HIGH	The access of users to CoE services is satisfactory, however a difficulty in migrating users from traditional delivery

					advertisement, etc) will be pushed and strengthened during the start-up of the CoE			channels to MaX User Portal is showing up. NEW MITIGATION ACTION: invest in the communication of the CoE User Portal NEW MITIGATION ACTION: use the very successful outreach channels (KPI-10) for the communication of the CoE User Portal
R9	There is limited interest in the end users for the commercial services of the CoE (<i>low risk</i>)	LOW	MED	WP5, WP6, WP7	In case of changing conditions T7.4 has been added explicitly to continuously monitor and assess the suitability of the current business model.	LOW-	MED	This risk is unchanged, but the recent activity demonstrates that commercial interest is high.
R10	The impact of the proposed activities into university courses might be limited and difficult to achieve within the project duration (<i>low risk</i>)	LOW	MED	WP5, WP6, WP7	The training modules developed will be sufficiently documented and presented such that they can also be utilised after the completion of the CoE.	LOW-	MED	The success of the training activity (KPI-11), indicates that the probability of occurrence of this risk is diminished.

APPENDIX 1 . Updated communication plan

General strategy (update)

Communication goals

The principal communications goals, as reported in D7.2 remain unchanged: promote a unified and coherent image of MaX, communicate clearly strategies and goals, enhance community identity, promote services, communicate major achievements, prepare CoE evolution. However, as MaX proceeded and interactions with its consumer base and stakeholders became more clear, we have decided to refocus the communication strategy on three new keywords: **codes, exascale, and co-design**. This implies a new modulation of the communication targets as well as of the communication channels and media.

The long value-chain of materials design, where MaX occupies the very first segment quite far from the materials end-users¹, poses additional challenges in the communication strategy to be adopted. In particular, social media communications are not very effective in this case, since they are more effective on the general public (segment 4 and 5 as defined in D7.2, reviewed in the present document, see section 4.4 below).

Shifting towards new communication keywords

A general trend in EU policies is clearly in the direction of HPC exascale targets. At the same time, the first two years of MaX have shown that the centre is recognized mostly for its excellence in the scientific actions, conjugated with its activity on exascale, co-design, and codes developments. For these reasons we decided to refocus the MaX communication strategy along these keywords, namely EXASCALE, CO-DESIGN and CODES, that will now be emphasized in addition to the more conventional keywords on materials design. A restructuring of the websites is planned for this scope (see the section below on websites convergence).

On the other hand, the first two keywords, although familiar to specialists, are obscure to the general public, and, for this reason, ineffective in social-media communication (possibly except for LinkedIn). Our strategy for the social-media presence will then not be affected by this decision, and will remain basically the one outlined in D7.2, with contents mostly focussed on communicating the “life” of the centre. We will possibly attempt communicating the concepts behind EXASCALE through simple and fast video pills from the MaX researchers, accompanied by a retrospective view: a series of tweets showing where the technology was in the past contrasted with where it is now.

New target segmentation (harmonizing industry, general and scientific targets)

Within the above framework, we will adopt a new communication target segmentation:

- 1) CODE DEVELOPERS - Communication Keyword: TECH-EXPERT
- 2) DOMAIN SCIENTISTS - Communication Keyword: EXCELLENCE
- 3) END-USERS and STAKEHOLDERS - Communication Keyword: TOP-NOTCH
 - a) MANUFACTURERS - Communication Keyword (specific): CODES & MATERIALS
 - b) MODELLERS - Communication Keyword (specific): CODES & CAPABILITIES
 - c) Software Vendors - Communication Keyword (specific): CODES & EXASCALE

¹ Here the term “end-user” is used with a different meaning with respect to that of communication target segmentation. In this case we refer to the typical end-user of the new materials, while in the case of communication target segmentation we refer to the end-users of MaX.

- d) Hardware companies - Communication Keyword (specific): CODESIGN & EXASCALE
- 4) SCIENCE INTERESTED PERSONS - Communication Keyword: DISCOVERY
- 5) CITIZENS - Communication Keyword: FUTURE

The categories the communication channels already identified in D7.2 for the main category of END-USERS and STAKEHOLDERS, namely, LinkedIn as the privileged social platform, and non-media communications such as the participation at sectorial fairs, the organisation and participation in congresses (with special emphasis on engineering oriented meetings) and schools, and the meetings with companies perdure.

Media and channels (websites, social media & others)

Long posts on linkedin will be written to promote codes (one for each code). And editorial plan of this action was agreed with partners. Our article in LinkedIn about HPC <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/designing-materials-high-performance-computing-guido-chiarotti> was quite popular (about 700 views, and about 50 resharing and likes), therefore we chose LinkedIn as the appropriate social media for this action. As discussed above, the communication strategy shift will have a minimum effect on our twitter presence, that will continue as outlined in D7.2.

In the following, we present some additional communication actions that will help us in managing the communication shift.

New communication actions

- MaX videos: a storyboard for a popular 110 sec video is ready and hopefully will be produced soon. We are also considering to produce a more technical and longer video.
- MaX prizes (see in section 1.2 above).
- MaX journalist-dedicated meeting: such a meeting is undergoing planning in collaboration with the Master in science communication at SISSA.

Convergence among institutional and industrial web sites

MaX website strategy was based on a twofold presence: the institutional site (www.max-centre.eu) and that dedicated to industries (www.max-centre.industries). This strategy was successful, as demonstrated by the number of visits, on both websites (slightly larger for the institutional one, as expected). However, we also noticed a kind of confusion in the audience due to this double presence. We added a number of interlinks (and more will be added) connecting the two websites, but the navigation experience is still not very satisfactory. For this reason we decided to completely review our web presence, converging on a single website both the institutional and the industrial dedicated part. A specific team (comprising both the scientific and the industrial MaX personnel, as well as the communication manager) will manage this action, that is planned to be completed by the end of the year.

We will profit of this step, for aligning the web presence to the new communication keywords: every code will have a **landing page** within the new MaX website, that, together with a popular description of the codes, will also contain:

1. a clear connection with the official code website
2. a banner with news highlights
3. a code download area

4. a workflow download area

It was agreed with the code owners that this new code specific pages will become the “official” popular pages of the codes, while the technical part will remain in the official code website.

Newsletter

We consider the first three numbers of MaX newsletter a very successful experiment (see above 1.4 and <http://www.max-centre.eu/newsletter/>). According to the communication shift, the newsletter will continue to be focussed on codes, exascale, co-design, and services. The number of subscribers is growing and is in the target.

Communicating MaX services

The MaX service User Portal communication plan was presented in D5.2. As discussed, the difficulty to move the users from the “old” operative modes to the User Portal can be ascribed to the communication strategy only in small part. However, a bigger effort in communicating the User Portal is probably necessary. We have profited of the last issues of the MaX newsletter to communicate the launch of the Users Portal and some of its services. Moreover, to increase the audience, we are planning to move some of the services (downloads and documentation) from the password protected area of the User Portal, to the free access MaX website (see the section on the MaX websites). The availability through the User Portal of the QaaS, a completely new service only available through this platform, will hopefully boost the increase the number of subscribers, that at the moment is stagnating.

APPENDIX 2. Specific actions report

LIST OF ACTIVITIES CARRIED OUT M7-M24
Main activities carried out with main results reported under each action
<p>Governance & management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Governance structure implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ finalized at M12 (see D7.2) ● Periodic updating of CoE objectives and tasks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ongoing activity ● Financial assessment and reporting <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ongoing activity ● Third party interactions, contracts and management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 signed contracts with peer partners ○ 1 signed contract with large industrial software vendor (Schroedinger, LLC) ○ 1 contract in negotiation with large cloud software provider ○ Additional third-party contacts (see also D5.3) ● Interactions with CoEs and others strategic EU consortium/entities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 4 MaX presentations to others CoE ○ ~20 MaX presentations to others EU consortium/entities ● International Advisory Board finalization and coordination ● KPI definition & KPI collection process design and implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ KPIs defined with intermediate targets at M6 (see D7.2) with integrations at M12 (see D7.3) ○ KPI collection process implemented at M6 connection to deliverables implemented at M18 ● Quality and Risk assessment design and management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ periodic risk assessment ongoing ● General Assemblies organization and reporting (minutes) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 4 GA organized and participated by all PIs or delegates (minutes available in the intranet website) ● M9 Brussels check assessment preparation and participation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MaX Spring Booklet preparation for presentation to the commission ○ participation of most PIs ● Trieste meeting (M17) organization and participation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ about 45 participants (see D7.5) ● Deliverables preparation and submission <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 16 deliverables submitted on time in the period ● Day-to-day management and coordination <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ongoing activity ● IP management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ SIESTA adopting an Open Source license; relicensing process managed by MaX ● Definition of a SME-oriented business model based on Quantum-as-a-Service

(QaaS)

- o Created and presented at M12 (see D7.4); ongoing improvement in collaboration with all partners integrating the individual software development processes

Services

- Services definition and deployment plan
 - o Initial services deployed. Service definition being extended with new services
- Services delivery process
 - o finalized at M12 (see D5.2)
- User Portal design and deployment
 - o First deployment with initial set of services at M9 (see D5.2), extended with dynamic services and TTS integration at M14 (see D5.3)
- Services & User Portal communication plan
 - o finalized at M12 (see D5.2)
- Users' management
 - o ongoing activity
 - o Services in support of partners for contractual, licensing and project planning
 - o Ongoing, used by one partner, under evaluation by others

Dissemination & communication

- Institutional Website design & deployment
 - o Number of unique visitors per month at M18: 2.200.
 - o Growth rate at M18: 5% per month.
- Industrial Website design & deployment
 - o Number of unique visitors per month at M18: 1.200.
 - o Growth rate at M18: 8% per month.
- MaX Intranet design & deployment
 - o ongoing development and integration process and continuous documentation updating
- Dissemination package preparation and delivery
- Inputs for communication activities
 - o ongoing activity by all partners
- MaX newsletter design and implementation
 - o 3 issues
- Social media communication
 - o ongoing activity